

Capillary rise with hydrostatic effects for wettability of small particles

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Abstract : To precisely and accurately measure wettabilities by capillary rise, an improved expression for this rise that incorporates hydrostatic effects was theoretically derived. Ceramic sand was tested by measuring the weight of liquid in a packed bed of deionized water and cyclohexane. Excellent agreement between the lipophilic to hydrophilic ratio (LHR) values calculated from our improved expression and those obtained by the equilibrium method was observed, validating our expression and confirming the suitability of the experimental method for small particles. Therefore, it should be possible to accurately measure the wettability of small particles as well as that of porous materials.

Keywords : Capillary rise, wettability, particle, filtration, packed bed, porous media.

Introduction

Wetting can be defined as the process by which one fluid phase is spontaneously displaced by another fluid from the surface of a solid or liquid. Wettability is a very important factor that affects the surface chemistry and natural phenomena exhibited by small particles and porous materials, especially in chemical, pharmaceutical and water treatment technologies, which all require knowledge of the wettability of small particles for production processes and product design¹⁻⁴. For example, oily water is a common waste stream in a wide range of industries, such as the steel, food, textile, leather, petrochemical and oil industries⁵. Deep bed filtration is technically and economically one of the most effective tertiary treatment procedures of oily water and is specially suited for treating oil particles smaller than 10 μm in low concentrations⁶. For deep bed filtration processes, a hydrophobic filter medium offers a better removal efficiency than a hydrophilic one. Capillary rise is an important way of determining the wettability of small particles and porous materials^{7,8}. However, wettability studies of small particles have always been questionable in terms of precision and reproducibility⁹.

In general terms, given that a packed particle column can be modeled as a bundle of uniform capillaries and

only laminar flow exists in the capillaries¹⁰, we can obtain the following equation by Poiseuille's law :

$$h^2 = \frac{\gamma r_{\text{eff}} \cos \theta}{2\eta} \quad (1)$$

where h is the height of the liquid penetrating the packed bed in time t , r_{eff} is the effective capillary radius, γ is the surface tension of the wetting liquid, η is the viscosity of the wetting liquid, and θ is the contact angle. Eq. (1) is the Washburn equation¹¹, which is widely applied to calculate the contact angle of small particles and porous materials.

We can calculate the contact angle by eq. (1) using curves representing the square of the penetration height h^2 versus time t , which constitutes the height method¹². However, to overcome the difficulties associated with the fact that the liquid front is not visible or the visible front does not accurately reflect the inner progression of the liquid in the packed bed, we can also choose to monitor the weight of the liquid in the packed bed or the increase in pressure in the tube to perform measurements, a technique referred to as the weight method^{13,14} or the pressure method^{15,16}. In practice, the r_{eff} values in eq. (1) vary between different particles in packed beds because the types, shapes and diameters of particles are different,

and it is rather difficult to calculate r_{eff} values directly and theoretically. However, when a total wetting liquid such as *n*-alkane is used, the contact angle of the liquid can be assumed to be zero, and as a result, r_{eff} can be obtained. It is hypothesized that a given packed bed exhibits the same r_{eff} value for different wetting liquids, namely, r_{eff} is a particle-specific property. In fact, r_{eff} is equal to r_d^2/r_s^{17} , where r_d is the equivalent hydraulic radius and r_s is the equivalent static radius. The same packed bed has the same r_s value because this parameter is only determined by the characteristics of a packed bed and is not related to the properties of wetting liquids. Nevertheless, r_d and r_{eff} , which depend not only on the characteristics of a packed bed but also on those of the wetting liquid¹⁸, vary between different wetting liquids even for the same capillary⁸ and packed bed. Consequently, the aforementioned hypothesis might introduce some errors into wettability calculations, although this problem has drawn little attention in the past. As a result, we may avoid considering the effects of the equivalent hydraulic radius r_d in the capillary rise method, leading to an easier method that considers hydrostatic effects for a more accurate and precise measurement of the wettability of small particles and porous materials.

Theory :

Height method :

Generally, a small-particle packed bed or porous material is assumed to behave as a bundle of capillaries, and only laminar flows exist in the cylindrical capillaries; thus, the overall balance of forces on the liquid in the capillaries takes the following form¹⁹ :

$$\rho\pi R^2\varepsilon\left(h\frac{d^2h}{dt^2}+\left(\frac{dh}{dt}\right)^2\right)+\frac{8\pi R^2\varepsilon\eta h}{r_d^2}\frac{dh}{dt}=\pi R^2\varepsilon\frac{2\gamma\cos\theta}{r_s}-\pi R^2\varepsilon\rho gh \quad (2)$$

where ρ is the density of the liquid and R and ε are the inner radius and porosity of the packed bed, respectively. The first term on the left side of eq. (2) gives the inertial resistance, whereas the second term represents the viscous resistance; on the other hand, the first term on the right side denotes the capillary pressure, and the last one

is the hydrostatic pressure. When the capillary radius is very small, viscous forces are dominant, and thus inertial effects can be neglected¹⁹. With the penetration of liquid into the packed bed, the hydrostatic effect becomes increasingly significant and cannot be neglected. In this case, one can solve the following equation :

$$\frac{8\eta h}{r_d^2}\frac{dh}{dt}=\frac{2\gamma\cos\theta}{r_s}-\rho gh \quad (3)$$

By integrating eq. (3), we obtain

$$\frac{\rho gr_d^2}{8\eta}t=-h-\frac{2\gamma\cos\theta}{\rho gr_s}\ln\left(1-\frac{\rho gr_s}{2\gamma\cos\theta}h\right) \quad (4)$$

Eq. (4) can be rewritten in the form of an infinite series as follows :

$$\frac{\rho gr_d^2}{8\eta}t=\frac{\rho gr_s}{4\gamma\cos\theta}h^2+\frac{h}{3}\left(\frac{\rho gr_s h}{2\gamma\cos\theta}\right)^2+\frac{h}{3}\left(\frac{\rho gr_s h}{2\gamma\cos\theta}\right)^3+\dots \quad (5)$$

To solve eq. (5), one can omit its higher-order remainder and obtain

$$\frac{r_d^2}{2\eta}t=\frac{r_s}{\gamma\cos\theta}h^2+\frac{\rho g}{3}\left(\frac{r_s}{\gamma\cos\theta}\right)^2h^3 \quad (6)$$

Combining eqs. (3) and (6), we obtain

$$\frac{\cos\theta}{r_s}=\frac{\rho g}{2\gamma}\left(\frac{1}{6(h-2v_h t)}h^2+\sqrt{\frac{h^4}{36(h-2v_h t)^2}+\frac{2h^3}{3(h-2v_h t)}}\right) \quad (7)$$

where $v_h = dh/dt$ represents the velocity at which the height of the liquid rises in the packed bed.

During the early stages of capillary rise, hydrostatic effects are very small and can be neglected. Thus, eq. (3) becomes

$$\frac{4\eta h}{r_d^2}\frac{dh}{dt}=\frac{\gamma\cos\theta}{r_s} \quad (8)$$

The integration of eq. (8) leads to the Washburn equation

(eq. (1)). In turn, during the early stages of capillary rise, the second term on the right side of eq. (6) is very small and can be neglected, which also yields the Washburn equation (eq. (1)).

Additionally, in the final stage, the velocity of the height of the liquid v_h as well as $v_h t$ are very small and can be neglected. Therefore, eq. (7) leads to

$$\cos \theta = \frac{r_s \rho g}{2\gamma} h \quad (9)$$

Eq. (7) is the equilibrium equation that is derived at the equilibrium state of capillary rise where $v_h = 0$. As a result, eq. (7) is as the same as the equilibrium equation (eq. (9)) during the final stage of capillary rise.

Experimental results show that eq. (7) is suitable for the latter stages of capillary rise, therefore confirming the validity of eq. (7). In this case, only $\cos \theta / r_s$ in eq. (7) is an unknown parameter, and the velocity of the height of liquid v_h can be deduced from height-time experimental data. Therefore, eq. (7) can be used to accurately calculate the value of $\cos \theta$.

Weight method :

The relationship between the height and weight of the liquid in the packed bed is

$$h = \frac{1}{\pi R^2 \varepsilon \rho} w \quad (10)$$

where w is the weight of the liquid penetrating the packed bed in time t . After modification, eq. (7) can be transformed into the following form for the weight method :

$$\frac{\cos \theta}{r_s} = \frac{g}{2\gamma\pi R^2 \varepsilon} \left(\frac{w^2}{6(w-2v_w t)} \right) + \sqrt{\frac{w^4}{36(w-2v_w t)^2} + \frac{2w^3}{3(w-2v_w t)}} \quad (11)$$

where $v_w = dw/dt$, represents the rate at which the weight of the liquid in the packed bed increases. Here, only $\cos \theta / r_s$ is an unknown parameter, and the rate of change in the weight of liquid v_w can be deduced from weight-time experimental data.

Eqs. (7) and (11) are improved expressions that we derived to calculate the contact angle θ by the height method

and the weight method, respectively. Clearly, errors in the calculation of θ introduced by the equivalent hydraulic radius r_d are eliminated because r_d is not involved in eqs. (7) and (11).

Experimental

Materials and reagents :

Ceramic sand with a size fractions ranging from +0.55 to 0.83 mm and density $\rho_s = 2300 \text{ kg/m}^3$, serving as the filter medium, and a packed bed with a porosity $\varepsilon = 0.490$ were selected for capillary rise measurements. The medium was purchased from Songxing Filter Plant, Henan, China. To remove the impurity on the filter medium surface, the filter medium was washing several times with deionized water after boiled in deionized water for 30 min, followed by until the washed water no longer appeared turbid. Before being used, the cleaned filter medium was dried at $110 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 12 h^{20} .

Apolar cyclohexane and polar deionized water were chosen as the oil phase and water phase²¹, respectively. The cyclohexane, which was analytically pure, was purchased from the Institute of Medicine Technology, Tianjin, China. The deionized water was produced by reverse osmosis, passed through two stages of a mixed ion exchange resin bed and a filtration stage involving activated carbon¹³. The characteristics of the two phases are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Characteristics of liquids at $20 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$

Wetting liquid	ρ (kg/m^3)	η ($\text{mPa}\cdot\text{s}$)	γ (mN/m)
Cyclohexane	778	0.973	25.5
Deionized water	998	1.002	72.8

Equipment and approach :

The weight method was adopted as capillary rise measurement, which was stated by our previous paper and the equipment is shown in Fig. 1²⁰. Shortly, a $10 \text{ mm} \times 150 \text{ mm}$ cylindrical glass tube made in our laboratory was equipped with a sintered glass sieve plate of controlled porosity at its bottom. An iron stand, which was placed on an automatic elevator platform, hung the filter medium particles packed glass tube. A glass beaker loading test liquids, whose temperature was strictly controlled to be approximately $20 \pm 0.5 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, was placed on the salver of an

Fig. 1. Schematic diagram of the measurement system used in the weight approach.

FA214 Model electronic balance equipped with a VBTERM Model processor. Both the electronic balance and processor were purchased from Shanghai Haikang Electronic Instrument Factory of China. The weight signal of the electronic balance was automatically recorded 5 times per second by a personal computer via a cable²⁰.

Before measurement, the elevator platform was activated to make the glass tube descend slowly. Once the surface of the liquid touched the bottom of the glass tube, the descent of the elevator platform was stopped. Then, capillary rise occurred, and the front of the liquid rose through the porous bed, causing the weight of the liquid in packed bed to increase. The elevator platform had to descend slowly at a very low speed of 10 mm/min controlled by the motor until the sintered glass filter just barely touched the test liquids. It should be noted that the packing procedure is the most important operation of the weight measurement method, so great care must be taken when preparing the packed bed to ensure reproducible results. Therefore, the packed glass tube was impacted manually hundreds of times until the height of the particles remained constant in the glass tube.

Results and discussion

Fig. 2d is plays the experimental results obtained for the capillary rise of the deionized water and cyclohexane as wetting liquids. In detail, Fig. 2a experimentally shows

the relation between the weight of the liquid in the packed bed w and time t . Fig. 2b shows the square of the weight w^2 as a function of time t , which was obtained from the data presented in Fig. 2a. The capillary rise exhibits behavior characterized by the relation $w^2 \propto t$ during the early stages, with slopes of 0.298 for deionized water and 0.124 for cyclohexane, which approximately represents the Washburn equation (eq. (1)).

Fig. 2. Experimental data of capillary rise for deionized water and cyclohexane : (a) The weight of liquid in packed bed w versus time t ; (b) The square of the weight w^2 versus time t .

We used eq. (11) to deduce the $\cos \theta/r_s$ values according to the experimental data as shown in Fig. 3. The term $\cos \theta/r_s$ reaches a plateau value after 20 s for cyclohexane and after 40 s for deionized water, as shown in Fig. 3a. The reason for these plateaus is that during the early stages of capillary rise, the surface tension is dominant and hydrostatic effects are trivial and can be neglected. Thereafter, the contact angle should not be determined using our improved expression during the early stages of the penetration process. However, at a later time, the liquid rises very slowly, and consequently, the weight increases very

Fig. 3. Values calculated by improved expression. (a) The $\cos \theta/r_s$ values deduced from the experimental data in Fig. 2(a) according to eq. (11); (b) The term $t \cos \theta/r_s$ versus time t .

slowly; thus, the dominant forces are indeed primarily due to surface tension and hydrostatic pressure. For this reason, extremely high-precision instruments are needed to record the weight values. Thus, whether the improved expression can be applied to measure the wettability of small particles depends on the instruments used and must be verified by experiment. As previously mentioned, a computer can automatically record much more accurate and precise data (5 data per second) than people can to ensure the precision and accuracy of data. In addition, the packing procedure must be strictly followed, and great care must be taken to ensure reproducibility. According to Fig. 3a, the term $t \cos \theta/r_s$ versus t after 20 s for cyclohexane and after 40 s for deionized water must be linear with slopes equal $\cos \theta/r_s$ and intercepts equal to zero, as shown in Fig. 3b. The slopes $\cos \theta/r_s$ of these lines are collected in Table 2. Linear least-square fits for all tests yielded regression coefficients greater than 0.999, confirming the good linearity of the results. It should be

Table 2. Summary of $\cos \theta/r_s$ values, in mm^{-1}

Wetting liquid	Eq. (11)	Equilibrium method
Deionized water	4.243	4.246
Cyclohexane	4.569	4.571

noted that every result expressed in this paper is the average value obtained for five reproducible experiments. Therefore, it can be concluded that measuring the wettability of small particles and porous materials using this improved expression is feasible.

To confirm the $\cos \theta/r_s$ values deduced from our improved expression, we used the equilibrium method to measure the $\cos \theta/r_s$ values. For the weight method, combining eqs. (9) and (10), the maximum weight of the liquid in a packed bed w_{eq} is given by

$$w_{\text{eq}} = \frac{2\gamma\pi R^2 \varepsilon \cos \theta}{g r_s} \quad (12)$$

Thus, the value of $\cos \theta/r_s$ can be calculated as

$$\frac{\cos \theta}{r_s} = \frac{g}{2\gamma\pi R^2 \varepsilon} w_{\text{eq}} \quad (13)$$

The values of the product $\cos \theta/r_s$ obtained from the equilibrium method (eq. (13)) is compared with that obtained from eq. (11) in Table 2. Table 2 indicates that the agreement between the $\cos \theta/r_s$ values calculated from the improved expression and equilibrium method for deionized water is extremely good. The same result is obtained for cyclohexane. This extremely high level of agreement further validates the improved expression and emphasizes its advantage : the two methods yield the same information regarding $\cos \theta/r_s$; however, the capillary rise method requires several hours to achieve the equilibrium state²¹. As a result, the equilibrium method is too time-consuming to be used in experiments, whereas the improved expression (eq. (11)) only requires data concerning the intermediate stages of capillary rise. Therefore, the improved expression is more convenient and more useful than the equilibrium method.

As previously mentioned, one can use a total wetting liquid (the contact angle of which is assumed to be zero) to calculate r_s from the values of the product $\cos \theta/r_s$ and

therefore obtain the contact angles of other liquids. However, a total wetting liquid cannot always be found for every filter medium. In these situations, the concept of the lipophilic to hydrophilic ratio (LHR) can be adopted¹³⁻¹⁵ :

$$\text{LHR} = \frac{\cos \theta_o}{\cos \theta_w} = \frac{\cos \theta_o / r_s}{\cos \theta_w / r_s} \quad (14)$$

Here, θ_o and θ_w are the contact angles of the filter medium for oil and water, respectively. Clearly, the LHR value reflects the difference in wettability selectivity of a certain type of filter medium between an apolar and polar liquid and also indicates the relative wettabilities of different types of filter media for oil and water.

To compare with the improved expression, the Washburn equation is also used to calculate the LHR value. For the weight method and according to eq. (11), the Washburn equation eq. (1) can be modified as follows :

$$wh^2 = (\pi R^2 \varepsilon \rho)^2 \frac{\eta_{\text{eff}} \cos \theta}{2\eta} t \quad (15)$$

Therefore, the slope k of eq. (15) is $(\pi R^2 \varepsilon \rho)^2 \frac{\eta_{\text{eff}} \cos \theta}{2\eta} t$,

and the LHR can be calculated as

$$\text{LHR} = \frac{\cos \theta_o}{\cos \theta_w} = \frac{2\eta_o k_o}{(\pi R^2 \varepsilon \rho_o)^2 \gamma_o r_{\text{eff}}} / \frac{2\eta_w k_w}{(\pi R^2 \varepsilon \rho_w)^2 \gamma_o r_{\text{eff}}} = \frac{\rho_w^2 \gamma_w \eta_o k_o}{\rho_o^2 \gamma_o \eta_w k_w} \quad (16)$$

Here, η_o and η_w , ρ_o and ρ_w , γ_o and γ_w , and k_o and k_w are the viscosities, densities, surface tensions and measurement curve slopes of oil and water, respectively.

The LHR values calculated from the improved expression (eq. (11)), equilibrium method (eq. (13)) and Washburn equation (eq. (15)) are 1.0768, 1.0765 and 1.8982, respectively. The LHR values calculated from the Washburn equation are significantly different from those calculated using the other two methods. One of the reasons for this difference is the effect of the hydraulic radius r_d , as previously mentioned. Another reason is related to the effects of the dynamic contact angle²². Common contact angle hysteresis theory assumes that liquid motion is suf-

ficiently slow to reach equilibrium. Thus, static values of the advancing contact angle and the receding contact angle may be involved. Fig. 2b demonstrates that the best of all possible fits of the square of the weight w^2 versus time t are between 0 and 15 s for deionized water and between 0 and 4 s for cyclohexane. At these stages, the liquid flow is relatively fast, as a result, the equilibrium contact angle θ_{eq} will be much less than the measured advancing contact angle; in other words, the $\cos \theta$ values calculated from the Washburn equation will be much lower than those calculated from the equilibrium method. Because the extent of dynamic contact angle effects varies between deionized water and cyclohexane, deviations will be introduced into the LHR values. However, the best of all possible fits to the slope of the improved expression are those for the later stages of capillary rise. During these stages, the liquid flow is very slow; consequently, the contact angle calculated from the improved expression (eq. (11)) is nearly equal to the equilibrium contact angle θ_{eq} . Therefore, there is excellent agreement with respect to the LHR values between our improved expression and equilibrium method.

Conclusions

To more accurately describe the relation between the weight of the liquid in a packed bed and time, by taking into account hydrostatic effects in the liquid penetration of spontaneous dynamic capillary rise, we have obtained an improved expression theoretically for capillary rise, which enables us to experimentally measure the contact angle of small particles precisely and accurately. The feasibility of the improved expression is confirmed by the high correlation coefficients. The excellent agreement between our improved expression and experimental data demonstrates the validity of the improved expression. Therefore, it should be possible to precisely and accurately measure the wettability of small particles and porous materials.

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References

1. Z. Hu, M. Gao, Z. Luo, Y. Ye and Y. Liu, *Colloids and Surfaces A : Physicochemical and Engineering Aspects*, 2014, **441**, 685.
2. M. A. Rodríguez-Valverde, F. J. Montes Ruiz-Cabello, P. M. Gea-Jódar, H. Kamusewitz and M. A. Cabrerizo-Vílchez, *Colloids and Surfaces A : Physicochemical and Engineering Aspects*, 2010, **365**, 21.
3. L. Susana, F. Campaci and A. C. Santomaso, *Powder Technology*, 2012, **226**, 68.
4. A. Waske, M. Heiland and S. Odenbach, *Chemical Engineering Science*, 2012, **76**, 192.
5. J. Mueller, Y. Cen and R. H. Davis, *Journal of Membrane Science*, 1997, **129**, 221.
6. T. Takahashi, T. Miyahara and Y. Nishizaki, *Chem. Eng. Jpn.*, 1979, **12**, 394.
7. L. Galet, S. Patry and J. Dodds, *Journal of Colloid and Interface Science*, 2010, **346**, 470.
8. H. Xue, Z. Fang, Y. Yang, J. Huang and L. Zhou, *Chemical Physics Letters*, 2006, **432**, 326.
9. A. Depalo and A. C. Santomaso, *Colloids and Surfaces A : Physicochemical and Engineering Aspects*, 2013, **436**, 371.
10. S. Levine, J. Lowndes, E. J. Watson and G. Neale, *Journal of Colloid and Interface Science*, 1980, **73**, 136.
11. E. W. Washburn, *Physical Review*, 1921, **17**, 273.
12. T. Subrahmanyam, M. Monte, A. Middea, E. Valdiviezo and F. Lins, *Minerals Engineering*, 1999, **12**, 1347.
13. B. Yang, Q. Chang, C. He and Y. Zhang, *Chemical Engineering and Processing : Process Intensification*, 2007, **46**, 975.
14. B. W. Yang and Q. Chang, *Separation and Purification Technology*, 2008, **60**, 335.
15. Q. Chang, B. Wei and Y. He, *Chemical Engineering Journal*, 2009, **150**, 323.
16. B. Wei, Q. Chang and C. Yan, *Journal of Colloid and Interface Science*, 2012, **376**, 307.
17. A. Siebold, A. Walliser, M. Nardin, M. Oppliger and J. Schultz, *Journal of Colloid and Interface Science*, 1997, **186**, 60.
18. A. Maestro, E. Guzmán, F. Ortega and R. G. Rubio, *Current Opinion in Colloid & Interface Science*.
19. A. Hamraoui and T. Nylander, *Journal of Colloid and Interface Science*, 2002, **250**, 415.
20. B. Wei, Q. Chang, C. Bao, L. Dai and G. Zhang, *Colloids and Surfaces A : Physicochemical and Engineering Aspects*, 2013, **434**, 276.
21. S. M. Iveson, S. Holt and S. Biggs, *Colloids and Surfaces A : Physicochemical and Engineering Aspects*, 2000, **166**, 203.
22. D. Myers, "Surface Interface and Colloids : Principles and Applications", 2nd ed., John Wiley & Sons, New York, 1999.

